

Electrochemical Reduction of *p*-Chlorobenzaldehyde at Copper and Amalgamated Copper Electrodes

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The reduction of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde has not been systematically studied¹. Polarographic reduction of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes have been studied in methanol solution². Kinetics of electrochemical reduction of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde was studied in aqueous acidic solutions at mercury pool electrode using controlled potential electrolysis and potentiostatic steady state techniques³. Reishakhrit and coworkers⁴ studied the polarographic reduction of benzaldehyde and its derivatives including *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde in aqueous ethanol solution. Voltammetric measurements of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde have also been studied by some workers⁵. Survey of literature reveals that reduction of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde has not been studied at metal electrodes except of some polarographic studies. *p*-Chlorobenzyl alcohol, one of the expected reduction product, is an industrially important compound. Reduction of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde has, therefore, been studied at different metal electrodes. Effects of various parameters, such as current density, temperature, concentration of depolariser and nature of cathode material on the yield percentage of *p*-chlorobenzyl alcohol have been studied in order to obtain optimum conditions for its synthesis.

Results and Discussion

Polarisation curves have been drawn between cathodic potential vs log current density (c.d.). Comparison of these curves in presence and in absence of depolariser shows that suitable current density ranges for reduction are 2.0–20.0 and 2.0–9.0 mA cm⁻² for copper and amalgamated copper electrodes respectively.

Various current densities were chosen and the experiments were conducted at each c.d. for both the electrodes. From the quantitative results of the product yield the favourable current densities are 6.0 mA cm⁻² for copper and 4.0 mA cm⁻² for amalgamated copper electrodes. Taking these optimum values of current density for each electrode different sets of experiments were conducted at different temperature, i.e. maximum product yield was obtained at 40° for both the cathodes.

To study the effect of medium concentration, different acid concentrations (5, 10, 15 and 20% w/v H₂SO₄) were taken, and 10% sulphuric acid concentration was found sufficient for maximum yield of the product.

The concentration of depolariser in electrolyte plays an important role in the electrochemical synthesis. It directly affects the yield of the product. For good yield, it is necessary to maintain the concentration of depolariser in the electrolyte. The percentage yield of the product at different depolariser concentrations, was studied at each electrode. Good yield was obtained at 0.20 *M* concentration of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde.

Electrode mechanism : The mechanism of the reduction of aldehydes in aqueous media involves two-electron reduction. Under acidic conditions, two one-electron waves are observed during linear sweep voltammetry (L.S.V.). In the first step the formation of ketyl anion free radical (II) takes place with one electron (eqn. 1),

This ketyl radical (II) may be further reduced (second wave) to the corresponding alcohol (III) (eqn. 2). Similar scheme may be proposed for the electroreduction reaction of *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde via the formation of $\text{ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}\cdot\text{OH}$. This is further supported by the working electrode potential vs time curves which show that the reaction is complete in the theoretical time required for two-electron on both the electrodes investigated⁶.

Experimental

p-Chlorobenzaldehyde (SISCO, L.R.) and sulphuric acid, potassium chloride, mercuric nitrate and sodium hydroxide (all excalar) were used. All solution were prepared in conductivity water. Experimental procedure used was same as reported earlier⁶. Cell assembly was composed of three compartments divided by a ceramic diaphragm. The reference electrode S.C.E. was connected to the cathode compartment with a Luggin capillary. Agitation of the catholyte was performed by magnetic stirring bar lead dioxide (3 × 4 cm; surface area 12.0 cm²) and Cu plate and Cu(Hg) (2 × 4 cm) as cathodes were used. The catholyte was prepared by dissolving *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde in

aqueous sulphuric acid solutions. The current regulated power supply used was developed by C.D.P.E., U.O.R., Jaipur. The cathodic potential was measured vs S.C.E. by digital multimeter. In all sets of experiments a theoretical quantity of current was passed depending upon the amount of depolariser taken.

After electrolysis the catholyte was filtered. The unreduced compound remained on filter paper and product went into the filtrate. The filtrate was neutralised with 5% sodium hydroxide solution to pH 6.5–7.0 and cooled to 5–10°. The solution was then extracted with ether (3 × 50 ml) and washed with ice-cold water to remove acid or salt (if any). The product was characterised by tlc, usual physicochemical methods and spectral analysis as *p*-chlorobenzyl alcohol.

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